

ECOLINGUISTICS: LANGUAGE AND ECOLOGY

Abdullaev Sobir Samadovich

Samarkand state institute of foreign languages.

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Abstract. *Ecolinguistics considers dialect in terms of interaction. It speaks to a certain act of interaction between person dialects or acts of interaction that emerge between individuals and countries with the assistance of dialect. For ecolinguistics, the protest is the characteristic environment for normal dialects. The advancement of ecolinguistics as a unused logical heading in phonetics permits us to consider issues of interaction between dialect and society, drawing on information from different logical areas:*

brain research, human science, reasoning. Ecolinguistics endeavors to cleanse the environment through simply phonetic implies. By making a difference to get it the components of compounding of clashes and the rise of debate, ecolinguistics tries to advance the peaceful coexistence of individuals totally different social bunches and in society. Environmental etymology is the consider of the forms of restraint or survival between competing dialects in a certain space, be it the intellect of an person or a society.

Key words: *Ecolinguistics, biolinguistics, microecolinguistics, macroecolinguistics, language ecology, ecological linguistics.*

ЭКОЛИНГВИСТИКА: ЯЗЫК И ЭКОЛОГИЯ

Аннотация. *Эколингвистика рассматривает диалект с точки зрения взаимодействия. Речь идет об определенном акте взаимодействия между диалектами людей или актах взаимодействия, возникающих между людьми и странами при помощи диалекта. Для эколингвистики протест — это характерная среда для нормальных диалектов. Выдвижение эколингвистики как неиспользуемой логической рубрики в фонетике позволяет рассматривать вопросы взаимодействия диалекта и общества, опираясь на информацию из разных логических областей:*

исследование мозга, гуманитарные науки, рассуждения. Эколингвистика стремится очистить окружающую среду посредством просто фонетических подразумеваний. Внося изменения, чтобы получить компоненты усугубления столкновений и возникновения дискуссий, эколингвистика пытается способствовать мирному сосуществованию людей из разных социальных групп и в обществе. Экологическая этимология — это рассмотрение форм сдерживания или выживания между конкурирующими диалектами в определенном пространстве, будь то интеллект человека или общества.

Ключевые слова: *эколингвистика, биоллингвистика, микроэколингвистика, макроэколингвистика, экология языка, экологическая лингвистика.*

As of now, natural issues are most regularly erroneously caught on basically as natural issues. In numerous ways, this perplexity of meaning happened due to the progressively substantial impact of people on the environment, but it is essential to isolated the concepts of biological (“related to the science of ecology”) and natural (“relating to the environment”). Common consideration to environment involved the development of the field of information (only organic)

at first very clearly characterized by Ernst Haeckel to other characteristic sciences and indeed the humanities.

Dialect is the living space of society, which employs it as one of its codes for putting away and transmitting natural (biosocial) encounter. The biological environment impacts an individual's etymological behavior and decides the elements of interaction. Concurring to Harald Haarmann, the most variables ("ecological variables") that decide the etymological behavior of social bunches and people incorporate: statistic, social, political, social, mental, connections and phonetic.

The term "biology" in connection to dialect was to begin with presented by John Trim. The concept of "linguistic ecology" was utilized by Karl and Francis Vogelin, who emphasized its important aspect - the got to consider in interaction all dialects spoken to in a certain range without exemption:

"In phonetic biology it is fundamental to begin not with a particular dialect, but with a certain domain, not with a particular consideration to a few dialects, and from thorough consideration to all dialects spoken to in a given territory" [8:2].

The reason of the ponder is to display ecolinguistics as a department of phonetics, provide it a common depiction, and analyze works on this issue.

Fabric and inquire about strategies

The fabric for the ponder was the works on phonetics by A.M. Molodkina, V.F. Nechiporenko, E. Haugen, H. Haarman, A. Fill.

To attain this objective, a hypothetical examination of the writing was utilized; Graphic, comparative-historical and comparative strategies were utilized.

Research results and discussion

The term "ecology" got to be most far reaching in etymology much obliged to the popular agent of the American department of sociolinguistics Einar Haugen. Since his book *The Biology of Dialect* was distributed in 1972, there has been quick improvement in this region. E. Haugen accepts that the subject of biology is the ponder of the results of a mental and social circumstance and its impact on a given dialect. He was moreover the primary to define the issues of dialect environment as a partitioned course by metaphorizing the concept of conventional biology. One of the arrangements he shaped states that dialects, like organic species, start, develop, alter, live and pass on in relationship with other dialects and their environment. Like natural species that are on the skirt of termination, dialects are too subject to a comparative peril, in this manner the biology of dialect, fathoming this issue, ought to offer ways to illuminate and avoid the passing of dialects [6:325].

Much obliged to the thoughts of E. Haugen, the fast development of ecolinguistics started in several bearings. Taking after him, the concept of ecolinguistics started to be created and refined by a number of other etymologists. German etymologist and social researcher Harald Haarmann recognized 7 "ecological variables", or variables that, in his supposition, decide the etymological behavior of both dialect bunches and people:

statistic, social, political, social, mental, connections and phonetic. These factors cannot be considered in segregation, since they are associated and associated with each other and themselves shape an "ecological system" [5:48].

As a term itself, the concept of “ecolinguistics” was presented by the cutting edge French etymologist orientalist, specialist in Arabic, African dialects and common phonetics Claude Agege in 1985. Since at that point, the concept “ecolinguistics” has been utilized as a covering assignment for “all logical areas of consider that interface biology with linguistics.” It is vital to recognize phonetic environment, which considers the connections between dialect and natural issues such as biodiversity and natural issues, from etymological environment, which is concerned with the intelligent between dialects, in specific the conservation of etymological differing qualities. Biological phonetics receives borrowed concepts and standards from environment in connection to dialect.

The premise of environmental considering is an understanding of systemic connections. A framework could be a entire comprising of a few parts, a set of components that are in certain connections with each other. This moreover applies to environment, which has as its fundamental question of consider biological systems, i.e. any community of living creatures beside their living space, associated with the inside and outside world by a complex framework of connections.

Ecolinguistic examination, firstly, relates phonetic information with the talking circumstance and the sociocultural and financial characteristics of the etymological society. Besides, since the all encompassing approach accept a see of the world in which everything is portion of an indissoluble entire, ecolinguistics does not decrease complex phenomena and frameworks to dualism, but portrays all wonders as:

- 1) interconnected (each unit of the total is associated with all other units and with the full);
- 2) interdependent (the hypostasis of the presence of a phonetic marvel changes on the off chance that another marvel ceases to exist);
- 3) connection (no unit impacts other units unless it is itself impacted; there's no unidirectional interaction; as it were two-way interaction, which, in any case, does not cruel symmetry, since one portion can overwhelm the others).

Third, ecolinguistics depends on a expressive outline that emphasizes the shared move of the particular and the common (widespread).

The all encompassing approach leads ecolinguists to common frameworks hypothesis and the concepts of open frameworks, flow, and rise. These hypothetical premises characterize dialect as a go between between social and common environments, and the term dynamism describes changes in individual, situational and social reality.

Ecolinguistics could be a modern department of etymology, which was shaped at the crossing point of social, mental and philosophical bearings in etymology. Ecolinguistics considers dialect in terms of interaction. Fair as environment considers the interaction of living living beings with each other and with the world around them, ecolinguistics analyzes the interaction between dialects, as well as dialects and their “environment,” that's , the society in which they are utilized.

Based on the over, ecolinguistics can be displayed as a unused segment of etymology, which was made on the principle of reflecting the concept of biology in science, the first meaning of which is the consider of the relationship of living beings with each other and the environment [7:93].

Agreeing to A.A. Polukhina, mindfulness of the marvel of ecolinguistics is inconceivable without considering present day philosophical sees on existing natural issues. It is the improvement

of philosophical thought, its neoclassical nature that gives the key to understanding ecolinguistics within the chain of greening and environmentalization of logical information on the way to a systemic (all encompassing, synergetic) turn in science within the context of the development of unused philosophical frameworks and ideal models of thinking [3:7].

Ecolinguistics is customarily isolated into large scale- and microecolinguistics.

Macroecolinguistics centers on issues of social, national, territorial and worldwide centrality. Microecolinguistics includes highlighting the study of discourse and dialect realities, taking into consideration components of an ecolinguistic arrange, including the conceptual angles of the hypothesis of dialect contacts, sociolinguistics, sociocultural anthropology, and psycholinguistics [1:5].

V.F. Nechiporenko incorporates ecolinguistics and biolinguistics . He centers on the reality that “ecolinguistics subordinates organic etymology and considers the last mentioned as one of its inside interrelated components.” Let us note that by biolinguistics the creator gets it “the science of connections, interconnects of fabric and otherworldly (mental) standards within the human body” [2:74]

Austrian etymologist Alwin Fill has created clear wording to apply to distinctive regions of ecolinguistics:

- ecolinguistics – a common term for all zones of inquire about that combine biology and etymology;
- environment of dialect (dialects) (Environment of dialect (s)) investigates the interaction between dialects (with the point of protecting etymological differing qualities);
- biological etymology (Biological etymology) forces terms and standards of environment on dialect (for case, the concept of an environment);
- phonetic (dialect) biology (Dialect biology, etymological environment) considers the relationship between dialect and “ecological” issues.

Conclusion

Summarizing the over, two bearings can be recognized in ecolinguistics:

- biology of dialect (concurring to E. Haugen), which allegorically exchanges environmental concepts into dialect (the exceptionally concept of biology, environment, environment): works by V. Trumpe, A. Fill , I. Storck , P. Finke;
- etymological environment (concurring to M. Halliday), in which dialects and writings are considered from the point of see of their “ biological neighborliness ” and the part of dialect in portraying the issues of the surrounding world is investigated - emphasizing and reinforcing them or understanding them: the works of M. Döring , P. Mühlhäusler .

In the event that auxiliary etymology separates dialect into partitioned components, ponders the restrictions of these units, recognizes between synchrony and diachrony, dialect and discourse, at that point environmental etymology emphasizes, rather than partition, the connection of components, rather than restrictions, their connections and maintains a strategic distance from recognizing between synchrony and diachrony. In structuralism, the meaning of an component is decided by its position within the framework. A system is something rather static, where each alter involves a alter within the equilibrium of the whole framework. On the opposite, an biological system is an open, living, energetic structure. The most protest of inquire about in ecolinguistics

isn't the state or advancement, not the connections between components, but the forms themselves and their interaction, driving to changes in components.

Not at all like chronicled etymology, which thinks about the impact of one dialect on another within the prepare of their improvement or the person advancement of dialects, environmental etymology ponders the forms of suppression or survival between competing dialects in a certain space, be it the awareness of an person or a society.

Compared to pragmatics, for which dialect may be a implies of communication for the trade of information and impact on other individuals, ecolinguistics thinks about the capacities of dialect, which are not constrained to the basic trade of “speech acts”. The function of dialect, which is to set up a association between individuals, gets to be more critical than a ask, an clarification, a address. Ecolinguistics ponders the part of dialect as a device for keeping up community and the working of this instrument in particular communication circumstances. By making a difference to get it the instruments of worsening of clashes and the emergence of issues, ecolinguistics tries to advance the tranquil coexistence of individuals totally different social bunches and in society [4:78].

One of the foremost vital criteria for the natural neighborliness of etymological units is their relationship with anthropocentrism. The ecolinguistic approach presupposes its possess translation of anthropocentrism, which is recognized by a basic demeanor towards the human-centric calculate, accepting that it gives rise to different ecolinguistic problems:

androcentrism, the belief system of the inexhaustibility of normal assets, categorization of the world from a human point of see. Anthropocentrism is additionally showed within the phonetic assignment of marvels of reality, considering them from the point of see of usefulness and futility for people. Anthropocentrism moreover incorporates a procedure of removing, emphasizing the division of man from nature. In case amid the arrangement of humankind such an approach to nature was essential for the survival of individuals as a species, at that point at show the divulgence of etymological appearances of these issues will contribute, on the one hand, to more noteworthy open mindfulness of the presence of these issues, and on the other, to their arrangement.

Ecolinguistics is called environmental etymology since it endeavors to cleanse the environment by phonetic implies. A astute human word can turn a part for the benefit of all humankind.

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